

lignosulphonate 0.05% at 20, 25, 30, 35 and 40°, has been reported by drop weight method^{9,10}.

Interfacial tension : The interfacial tension data of the above formulations against kerosene oil and turpentine oil have been used from the author's earlier work¹¹. All the experiments were conducted at 25±1°.

Calculations of spreading coefficient, Girifalco-Good's constant and liquid/liquid interface interaction : The spreading coefficient, Girifalco-Good's constant, and liquid/liquid interface interaction of above formulations at kerosene and turpentine oil surfaces have been calculated from the following expressions, respectively¹²

$$S = Y_w - (Y_o + Y_{ow}) \quad (1)$$

$$Y_{ow} = Y_o + Y_w - 2\theta(Y_o \times Y_w)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Liquid/liquid interface interaction} = Y_{ow}^{\text{cal}} - Y_{ow}^{\text{obs}} \quad (3)$$

where S is spreading coefficient ; Y_w , surface tension of aqueous phase ; Y_o , surface tension of oil phase ; Y_{ow} , interfacial tension ; θ , Girifalco-Good's constant ; Y_{ow}^{cal} , calculated interfacial tension ; and Y_{ow}^{obs} , experimental interfacial tension.

The results are presented in Tables 1-3.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF LIGNOSULPHONATE CONCENTRATION ON INTERMOLECULAR FORCES

Lignosulphonate Concn. %	Kerosene oil			Turpentine oil		
	S erg cm ⁻²	ϕ	excess energy	S erg cm ⁻²	ϕ	excess energy
0.01	19.05	0.84	+19.05	23.40	0.87	+23.40
0.02	15.91	0.87	+15.91	22.41	0.93	+22.41
0.04	15.89	0.90	+15.89	21.53	0.96	+21.53
0.08	15.29	0.93	+15.29	20.10	0.97	+20.10
0.10	9.69	0.91	+9.69	14.44	0.95	+14.44

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ALCOHOL-CARBON CHAIN LENGTH Lignosulphonate concn. = 0.05% (w/v) Alcohol concn. = 0.1% (v/v)

Alcohol	Kerosene oil			Turpentine oil		
	S erg cm ⁻²	ϕ	excess energy	S erg cm ⁻²	ϕ	excess energy
CH ₃ OH	25.70	0.96	+25.70	29.80	0.99	+29.80
C ₂ H ₅ OH	7.45	0.89	+7.45	10.95	0.91	+10.95
C ₃ H ₇ OH	20.90	0.82	+20.90	-17.35	0.82	+17.35
C ₄ H ₉ OH	25.55	0.91	+22.55	-22.40	0.89	-22.40
C ₅ H ₁₁ OH	28.35	1.01	-18.35	-25.20	0.98	-25.20

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF SALINITY Lignosulphonate concn. = 0.05% (w/v)

NaCl %	Kerosene oil			Turpentine oil		
	S erg cm ⁻²	ϕ	excess energy	S erg cm ⁻²	ϕ	excess energy
0.01	10.11	0.80	+10.11	14.94	0.83	+14.94
0.02	13.56	0.87	+13.56	19.66	0.92	+19.66
0.04	14.13	0.90	+14.13	19.63	0.95	+19.63
0.08	14.37	0.98	+14.37	19.25	0.97	+19.25
0.10	12.27	0.92	+12.77	17.49	0.96	+17.40

Results and Discussion

The results of spreading coefficients presented in Tables 1-3 show that higher lignosulphonate concentration and high temperature, lower the spreading coefficient and hence increase the spreading nature while higher salinity increases the non-spreading nature of aqueous phase containing lignosulphonate. Table 2 depicts that CH₃OH and C₃H₇OH favour spreading nature but for C₄H₉OH to C₅H₁₁OH, the spreading coefficient has negative values, thereby depicting a high cohesion and non-spreading nature.

Girifalco-Good's constant data show that higher concentration of lignosulphonate and salinity favour hydrogen bonding between oil and surfactant solutions while temperature disfavours this phenomenon. This is in agreement with the fact that for hydrogen bond formation in both the liquids, Girifalco-Good's constant must be greater than 0.84 value¹.

The calculated and observed interfacial tension data and liquid-liquid interaction (by assuming only dispersive force interactions at the surface) indicate that with the exception of C₃H₇OH to C₅H₁₁OH, Y_{ow}^{cal} is greater than Y_{ow}^{obs} , the excess energy may be attributed to the interaction between phases.

References

1. L. A. GIRIFALCO and R. J. GOOD, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1957, **61**, 904.
2. F. M. FOWKES, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, **66**, 1869.
3. F. M. FOWKES, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, **67**, 2533.
4. F. M. FOWKES, "Adhesion", ASTM Spec. Tech. Pub., 1964, No. 360.
5. F. M. FOWKES, "Advances in Chemistry", 1964, **43**, 59-111.
6. F. LONDON, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1937, **8**, 33.
7. J. H. HILDEBRAND and R. L. SOOFT, "Regular Solution", Practice-Hall, Angewood Cliffs, 1962, pp. 79-80.
8. J. H. HILDEBRAND and R. L. SOOFT, "Solubility of Non-electrolytes", 3rd ed., Reinhold, New York, 1950.
9. W. D. HARKINS and F. E. BROWN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, **38**, 499.
10. W. D. HARKINS and F. E. BROWN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, **41**, 228.
11. W. U. MALIK, S. K. SRIVASTAVA, T. CHAND and A. K. JINDAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 1053.
12. F. M. FOWKES, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1964, **40**, 13, 56.

Studies on Arndt-Eistert Synthesis : Synthesis of N-Aryl-N'-3-methyl- caproylurea Derivatives

K. R. DESAI and M. M. PATHAK

Department of Chemistry, South Gujarat University,
Surat-395 007

Manuscript received 15 February 1984, revised 24 May 1984,
accepted 10 August 1984

UREA derivatives possess wide therapeutic activity such as antibacterial¹, antithyroid, hypnotic and anesthetic, hypoglycemic², anthelmintic, diuretic³ and biocidal. Phenylacetamidourea derivatives are active anticonvulsants.

Arndt-Eistert⁴ and Robinson and Bradley prepared diazoketones from acid chlorides with diazomethane. From this diazoketone various phenylurea derivatives were prepared. Optically active phenylurea derivatives were prepared to study whether optical activity remains or not. Optically active *S*-(-)-2-methylbutane-1-ol (I), $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 4.62$ ($l=1$) on bromination with red phosphorus and liquid bromine resulted in *S*-(+)-2-Me-1-bromobutane (II), $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 1.69$ ($l=1$). It was then treated in ether with magnesium turnings, and carbon dioxide to give optically active *S*-(+)-2-methylvaleric acid (III), $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 4.66$ ($l=1$). The acid chloride (IIIa) was obtained with thionyl chloride. Diazomethane was reacted with 2-methylvaleryl chloride to yield *S*-(+)-3-methylcaproic acid (IV), $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 4.75$ which with thionyl chloride afforded *S*-(+)-3-methylcaproyl chloride (IVa), $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 4.88$. The latter was condensed with different phenylureas to give optically active *N*-aryl-*N'*-3-methylcaproylureas (V).

I: R=OH; II: R=Br; III: R=COOH; IIIa: R=COCl
 IV: R=CH₂COOH; IVa: R=CH₂COCl;
 and V: R=CH₂CONHC₆H₅.

Experimental

Infrared spectra (nujol) were recorded with a Beckman Model IR-5 spectrometer equipped with NaCl prism.

S-(-)-2-Methylbutane-1-ol⁵: Fusel oil contains as one of the constituents optically active *S*-(-)-2-methylbutane-1-ol which was obtained by fractional distillation, b.p. 126-28°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 4.62$ ($l=1$); d_4^{25} , 0.8279; η^{25} , 1.450.

S-(+)-2-Methyl-1-bromobutane: A mixture of *S*-(-)-2-methylbutane-1-ol (440 g, 5 mol) and pure red phosphorus (31.06 g) was refluxed on a water bath and bromine (400 g, 129.2 ml) was introduced from a separating funnel into the mixture during 2 h at such a rate that there was always a little bromine vapour above the surface of the reaction mixture. The reaction mixture was further refluxed for 1 h and then distilled. Most of the bromobutane was collected at 112-22°. The latter was washed successively with water, an equal volume of conc. hydrochloric acid, and sodium bicarbonate solution (10%), and finally with water and dried with anhydrous calcium chloride. Redistillation at 116-18° gave the pure compound (57%) which was confirmed by tlc, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 1.69$ ($l=1$); d_4^{25} , 1.255; η^{25} , 1.455.

S-(+)-2-Methyl-1-valeric acid: In a three necked R.B. flask fitted with a mercury seal stirrer, reflux condenser and dropping funnel, were placed magnesium turnings (24.3 g), dry ether (300 ml) and

also some iodine crystals. A solution of 2-methyl-1-bromobutane (151 g, 1M) in absolute dry ether was added from the dropping funnel. The reaction started after 3 min with disappearance of the iodine colour. The addition of bromobutane solution was continued dropwise at such a rate that the reaction did not become vigorous. Bromide in ether was added in 2 h and the reaction mixture was refluxed on warm water bath for 1 h.

Dry CO₂ gas was passed for 2-3 h below -5° and the whole mixture kept overnight. It was then decomposed by aqueous NH₄Cl solution (10%). The ethereal layer was treated with aqueous NaOH (2N). The aqueous layer was acidified and extracted with ether. Ethereal layer was dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and on evaporation the residual *S*-(+)-2-methylvaleric acid was purified by distillation at 197-98° (60%), $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 3.76$ ($l=1$); d_4^{25} , 0.9636; η^{25} , 1.441.

S-(+)-2-Methylvaleryl chloride: In a R.B. flask thionyl chloride (1.5 mol) and *S*-(+)-2-methylvaleric acid (1.0 mol) were heated on a water bath for 0.5 h. *S*-(+)-2-Methylvaleryl chloride was distilled at 140-45° (80%), $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 2.65$ ($l=1$); d_4^{25} , 0.9302; η^{25} , 1.434.

Diazoketone⁶: In a R.B. flask containing the mixture of ether (500 ml) *S*-(+)-2-methylvaleryl chloride (2 g) and solution of diazomethane in ether was placed at 20-25° for 3-4 h. Ether was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was diazoketone.

S-(+)-3-Methylcaproic acid: The diazoketone was mixed with dioxane (88 ml) and was treated with a mixture of silver oxide (2 g), anhydrous sodium carbonate (5 g), anhydrous sodium thiosulphate (3 g) in water (200 ml) and stirred at 55-60°. The temperature was raised to 90-100°, cooled, diluted with water and acidified to obtain *S*-(+)-3-methylcaproic acid. It was distilled at 208-9° (65%). The purity was checked by tlc (Found: C, 64.25; H, 10.19 and O, 24.09%); $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 4.21$ ($l=1$); d_4^{25} , 1.0230; η^{25} , 1.417.

S-(+)-3-Methylcaproyl chloride: In a R.B. flask, thionyl chloride (1.5 mol) and 3-methylcaproic acid (1 mol) were refluxed for 0.5 h. *S*-(+)-3-Methylcaproyl chloride was distilled at 167-70° (57%); $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 4.01$ ($l=1$); d_4^{25} , 0.9970, η^{25} , 1.404.

General method for preparation of optically active *S*-(+)-3-methylcaproylurea derivatives: A mixture of 3-methylcaproyl chloride (0.05 mol) and various phenylureas in rectified spirit was refluxed for 2 h. The cooled mixture deposited a solid which was washed with hydrochloric acid (2N) and then with water. The product was crystallized from ethanol.

Melting points of the compounds are mentioned below: R₁=phenyl, 135-36°; *o*-tolyl, 155-56°; *m*-tolyl, 115-16°; *p*-tolyl, 160°; *m*-nitrophenyl, 90°; *p*-nitrophenyl, 133°; *m*-chlorophenyl, 100°; and *p*-chlorophenyl, 190°.

In these optically active phenylurea derivatives, the maximum rotation was found in the case of *N-m*-nitrophenyl-*N'*-3-methylcaproylurea, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 110.5$ ($l=1$) and the minimum in the case of *N-m*-tolyl-*N'*-3-methylcaproylurea, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 25.5$ ($l=1$).

Infrared spectra: All the compounds, in general gave the following bands: 1500-1480 (NH stretch), 1690-1570 (C=O stretch), -CO.NH.CO- stretching vibration 1640-1740 (CO.NH.CO stretch) and 710-690 cm^{-1} (CH stretch).

Antibacterial activity: The purified product was screened for antibacterial activity by cup-plate method using a species of gram-positive bacteria, *i.e.* *S. aureus* and a species of gram-negative bacteria, *i.e.* *E. coli*. Testing was carried out in ethanol solution at the concentration of 10 mg ml^{-1} .

The zone of inhibition of the test solutions were recorded.

The zone of inhibition against *S. aureus* was found maximum in the case of *N-o*-tolyl-*N'*-3-methylcaproylurea (8 m.m.) and minimum for *N-p*-tolyl-*N'*-3-methylcaproylurea (3 m.m.).

Similarly, for *E. coli* the maximum zone was found for *N-m*-chlorophenyl-*N'*-3-methylcaproylurea (5 m.m.) and minimum value occurred in the case of *N-p*-nitrophenyl-*N'*-3-methylcaproylurea (2 m.m.).

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to South Gujarat University for providing facility and to U.G.C., New Delhi for awarding Junior Research Fellowship to one of the authors (M.M.P.).

References

1. R. H. WILLIAMS and E. G. FRANK, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1946, 40, 54905.
2. H. FRANK and K. K. PATNAIK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 27, 535.
3. W. L. LIPSCHITZ and E. STOEKEY, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1945, 39, 48955.
4. F. ARNDT, B. EISTERT and W. PARTIAR, *Chem. Ber.*, 1927, 60, 1364.
5. E. L. BADIM and E. PASCU, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 60, 1968.
6. F. ARNDT and J. AMENDE, *Chem. Ber.*, 1928, 61, 1122.

Studies on Chalcones: Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-Aryl-4-carboxy-6-acetylquinoline and 2-Aryl-4-carboxy-6-benzalacetquinolines

D. J. BHATT, G. C. KAMDAR and A. R. PARIKH

Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University,
Rajkot-360 005

Manuscript received 25 July 1983, revised 21 April 1984,
accepted 15 August 1984

QUINOLINE derivatives possess wide therapeutic activity, *viz.* antiseptic¹, analgesics², tryphocidal³, germicidal⁴, antitubercular⁵, anthelmintics⁶ and antiserotonin⁷. Chalcones also possess anthelmintic⁸,

antimitotic and antimicrobial activity¹⁰. With a view to prepare better therapeutically active compounds, we have synthesised 2-aryl-4-carboxy-6-acetylquinoline of type (I)¹¹ and condensed them with benzaldehyde to get chalcones (II). The constitutions of acetoquinoline and chalcone were supported by ir spectra. The ir spectra (KBr) of 2-phenyl-4-carboxy-6-acetylquinoline and 2-phenyl-4-carboxy-6-benzalacetquinolines showed bands at 1490 (C=N) and 1590 (C=C), 1360 (CH₃-CO) 1440 (COOH), and 1480 (C=N), 1590 (C=C), 1310 (CH=CH), 1670 (C=O) and 1440 cm^{-1} (COOH), respectively¹². The products were screened for antibacterial activity.

where R = Aryl

Experimental

2-Aryl-4-carboxy-6-acetylquinoline: A mixture of purified benzaldehyde (0.01 mol), freshly distilled pyruvic acid (0.01 mol) and absolute ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed and a solution of *p*-aminoacetophenone (0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol (25 ml) was added slowly with frequent shaking. The mixture was further refluxed for 3 h and allowed to stand overnight. The product was filtered and crystallised from ethanol. The physical constants are recorded in Table 1.

2-Aryl-4-carboxy-6-benzalacetquinolines: Benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in ethanol (95%, 10 ml) was added to the mixture of 2-aryl-4-carboxy-6-acetylquinoline (0.01 mol) in ethanol (95%, 25 ml), aqueous sodium hydroxide (1%, 6 ml) and rectified spirit (95%, 10 ml) and stirred at 20-30° for 2-3 h. Content were then kept for 24 h at 0-10°, filtered and the product was isolated by acidification and crystallised from ethanol. The physical constants are recorded in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

Antimicrobial activity: The purified products were screened for antibacterial activity by cup-plate method¹³ using a species of gram-positive bacteria, *i.e.* *Staphylococcus aureus* and a species of gram-negative bacteria, *i.e.* *Escherichia coli*. The testing was carried out in ethanol at a concentration of